

THE GOOD IN THE BAD: COVID-19 Lockdown and Air Quality in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 was declared as a pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) on March 11, 2020, marking one of the greatest challenges to global health in modern history, 40–60% of the global population was predicted to get infected. To curtail the virus's spread, a statewide lockdown was declared in Nigeria on March 30, 2020. This study investigates the improvement in air quality resulting from the lockdown, largely due to the reduction in human activities and corresponding emissions of primary air pollutants. Using satellite-derived data from NASA's Giovanni platform, March and April 2020 monthly data were contrasted with three-year monthly averages for the same period (2017–2019). Findings revealed a significant decline in PM_{2.5} (–76.16%) and NO₂ (–6.57%) in March 2020, accompanied by a 0.90% increase in ozone column concentrations. In April 2020, reductions were also recorded in PM_{2.5} (–16.37%), NO₂ (–4.68%), and SO₂ (–1.10%), while total ozone column rose by 0.47%. These pollutant-specific responses highlight the sensitivity of air quality to emission reductions and the complexity of atmospheric interactions. Although the lockdown yielded positive environmental outcomes, including improved air quality, it also came with severe economic and social consequences, alongside the tragic loss of lives to the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria.

1. Introduction

In March 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) proclaimed the novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) to be a global pandemic; this ushered in an unprecedented era of global lockdown and mobility restrictions [1]. At the end of 2019, an unidentified acute pneumonia at Wuhan Hospital in Eastern China became the very first incident of COVID-19. The Country Office of the World Health Organization (WHO) in Wuhan, China, received this information on December 31, 2019. Consequently, the Director General of the WHO declared COVID-19 a pandemic on 11th March [2, 3].

However, in Nigeria, the Federal Ministry of Health confirmed its first case on the 27th of February 2020. Contact tracing was done and the people involved were taken into isolation for monitoring and testing in an effort to minimize the virus's spread. Thereafter, as the infected persons kept increasing, on March 30, 2020, the Federal Government of Nigeria, acting through its agency, the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC), immediately imposed a nationwide lockdown in the three most affected states of the Federation: Lagos, Ogun, and Abuja, which was later extended to Kano.

This included the closure of restaurants, schools, hotels, clubs, road transportation garages, airports and train stations. Larger gatherings like Churches, Mosques, Markets, social events/parties were also suspended. The lockdown was a mandatory preventive measure; federal government agencies were on total lockdown, and citizens were instructed to sit at home to observe COVID-19 rules [4]. The imposed total lockdown resulted into economic hardship in the country leading to loss of jobs and crashing of businesses. The Nigerian government decided to gradually lift the country's lockdown to mitigate financial chaos. On April 27, 2020, the President announced the first phase of the lockdown easing, starting on the 4th of May, in lieu of this, Nigerian experienced pre-lockdown, lockdown, and gradual easing up of lockdown during the Covid-19 pandemic in the year 2020. The pre-lockdown lasted 31 days (February 28–March 29, 2020), the total lockdown lasted 35 days (March 30–May 3, 2020), and the gradual lifting of the lockdown lasted 73 days (May 5–July 15, 2020) [5]. In this study, March 2020 is considered a partial lockdown period as the lockdown was declared nationwide on the 30th of March, covering only the final two days of the month, while April 2020 represents the full lockdown period. The analysis uses monthly averages for these periods compared to the 2017–2019 baseline. Generally, the purpose of imposing lockdown was to make the Covid-19 curve flatten, minimize the virus's spread, isolate the infected persons and to ensure they were given proper treatment to recover as quickly as possible.

Governments worldwide imposed a range of containment measures, which includes travel bans, stay-at-home orders, industrial shutdowns, and reduction in public and private transportation. These temporary interventions, although primarily health-focused, was done to reduce the virus's spread, they ultimately led to significant environmental changes, most notably and obvious in air quality [6, 7, 8].

Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation, has encountered serious challenges related to ambient air pollution, particularly in urban and industrial zones. Key pollutants such as nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), ground-level ozone (O₃) and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and have been linked to poor air quality in major cities like Lagos, Port Harcourt, Kano, and Abuja [9]. Sources of air pollution in Nigeria include industrial discharges, vehicle emissions, open waste burning, and high reliant on fossil-fuel-powered transportation [10]. Studies have shown that air quality in Nigeria regularly transcend WHO guideline limits, posing severe public health risks, which includes respiratory diseases, cardiovascular complications, and premature deaths [11, 12, 13]. Regardless of the gravity of the problem, systematic monitoring of air quality in Nigeria remains limited due to insufficient ground-based stations and weak enforcement of environmental regulations. Satellite-based remote sensing tools such as

NASA's Giovanni data system have therefore become progressively valuable for temporal and spatial monitoring of air pollutants across the country [14].

The period of lockdown due to COVID-19 represents a natural experiment for assessing the effect of anthropogenic emissions on ambient air quality. While similar studies have been extensively done in other regions, limited empirical evidence exists for West Africa, particularly Nigeria. In Salé City, Morocco, pollutant concentrations changed significantly during the lockdown period compared to before lockdown, with reductions of 75% for PM₁₀, 49% for SO₂, and 96% for NO₂. Notably, PM₁₀ concentrations decreased less dramatically than NO₂ levels [15]. In contrast to an average increase of 23.7% over the same periods in the preceding five years, the 30-day mean PM_{2.5} concentration in Seoul, South Korea, dropped by 10.4% in 2020. The city-wide drop in PM_{2.5} concentrations was more noticeable during the day than at night. Meanwhile, NO₂ and CO concentrations fell by 16.4% and 16.9%, respectively. [16]. In São Paulo, Brazil, air quality improved during the 2020 partial lockdown, with average hourly concentrations of CO, NO, NO₂, and PM_{2.5} dropping by 38.8%, 44.9%, 38.7%, and 6%, respectively, compared to pre-pandemic levels, according to data from CETESB monitoring facilities in the Metropolitan Area of São Paulo. [17]. In Bogotá, Colombia's capital, and northern regions, PM_{2.5} levels dropped significantly, with decreases of 68% and 86%. This reduction is linked to decreased vehicular traffic during the lockdown period. [18]. Prior to and following the start of the quarantine, data on PM_{2.5} emissions from the world's 50 most polluted capitals, as determined by the World Health Organization, showed an average 12% reduction in PM_{2.5} [19]. Also, data from ESA (European Space Agency) and NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) indicates that pollution decreased by up to 30% in some of the COVID-19 epic centers, including Wuhan, Italy, Spain, and the USA [20].

While similar studies have been extensively conducted in other regions, empirical evidence for West Africa, particularly Nigeria, remains limited due to insufficient ground-based monitoring infrastructure and documented research on lockdown-related air quality changes in the region.

This study investigates the changes in air quality in Nigeria during the COVID-19 lockdown by analyzing atmospheric concentrations of PM_{2.5}, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃ using satellite-derived data from NASA's Giovanni platform. By comparing pollutant levels during the lockdown year (2020) with the preceding three years (2017–2019), the research aims to quantify the extent to which the COVID-19 lockdown impacted air quality in Nigeria. This study is particularly important in providing empirical evidence to hold up sustainable environmental and urban planning

strategies, especially in post-pandemic recovery policies. It also emphasizes the significance of incorporating air quality considerations into public health decision-making.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

This study focuses on Nigeria, located in West Africa between latitudes 4° and 14° N and longitudes 3° and 15° E. Nigeria is characterized by different ecological zones ranging from the coastal mangrove swamps in the south to the Sahel savannah in the north. The country is the most populous in Africa and one of the fastest urbanizing regions globally, with major cities including Lagos, Abuja, Kano, and Port Harcourt contributing significantly to anthropogenic emissions [21]. The geographic scope of this study spans the entire Nigerian territory as shown in figure 1, enabling a comprehensive national assessment of ambient air quality changes.

Fig 1. Map of Nigeria showing major cities (Lagos, Abuja, Kano, Port Harcourt) relevant to this air quality study. The map illustrates the geographical scope spanning longitudes 3° to 15°E and latitudes 4° to 14°N (Source: <https://ncdc.gov.ng>).

2.2. Data Source and Description

Air quality data for this study were obtained from the Giovanni online data system (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/giovanni/>), a web-based platform developed and maintained by the NASA Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center (GES DISC). Giovanni enables interactive visualization and download of satellite-based Earth science data without the need for specialized software or high-performance computing resources [22].

Atmospheric air quality is commonly assessed through a set of key pollutants, which include particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), gaseous pollutants such as Nitrogen

dioxides (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), Carbon monoxide (CO), Ozone (O₃), and heavy metals like lead (Pb). Additional indicators include volatile organic compounds (VOCs), hydrocarbons (HC), dust deposition, and indices of sulphate and fluoride concentrations. These parameters are systematically monitored and reported under Ambient Air Quality Standards to evaluate their impacts on the environment and human health [23, 24, 25].

The following atmospheric air quality parameters were selected for analysis due to their relevance to public health and atmospheric chemistry:

Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}): A complex mixture of liquid and solid particles that are suspended in the air is known as atmospheric particulate matter. Fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) is the portion of inhalable particulate matter that is smaller than 2.5 micrometers and can be deeply breathed into the lungs (U.S. EPA, 2018). The monthly Dust surface Mass Concentration-PM_{2.5} data were downloaded from the Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications, Version 2 (MERRA-2), which assimilates aerosol optical depth (AOD) and provides global PM_{2.5} estimates at 0.5° × 0.625° resolution [26].

It is important to note that the MERRA-2 PM_{2.5} data represents primarily dust surface mass concentration, which captures mineral dust aerosols dominant during Nigeria’s dry season and harmattan period. While this is highly relevant for Nigeria’s air quality assessment, it may not fully capture all anthropogenic PM_{2.5} components from urban sources such as vehicle emissions, industrial activities, and biomass burning. The total PM_{2.5} includes both natural dust and anthropogenic particulate matter, and the MERRA-2 reanalysis assimilates these components.

Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂): Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) is a gaseous air pollutant produced primarily by the fossil fuels combustion, especially from motor vehicles, power plants, and industrial activities [24].

NO₂ data were Obtained from the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) aboard NASA’s Aura satellite, using Level-3 gridded tropospheric column densities.

Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂): This gas result from the burning of Sulphur or materials containing Sulphur. The largest sources of its emissions into the air are from fossil fuel combustion at power plants and other industrial facilities [24]. The monthly data SO₂ Surface Mass Concentration of the source MERRA-2 Model with spatial resolution 0.5 X 0.625°, measured in Kgm⁻³ was downloaded for this analysis.

Ozone (O₃): Total column ozone is the total amount of ozone in a column extending vertically from the earth’s surface to the top of the atmosphere. The ozone hole is

defined in terms of reduced total column ozone, less than 220 Dobson Units (DU), where Dobson Units measure the total amount of ozone in a vertical column of the atmosphere. Natural chemical interactions between oxygen molecules and solar UV rays (below 242 nm) produce stratospheric ozone. It plays a vital role in protecting humans and other life forms by absorbing harmful UV radiation from the sun, preventing it from reaching the Earth's surface [27].

Ozone Total Column (TOMS-like) daily data of source OMI with spatial resolution of 0.25° were downloaded for this work.

All datasets were acquired as monthly averages for March and April of each study year (2017, 2018, 2019, and 2020). The data were pre-processed on the Giovanni platform using regional bounding boxes for Nigeria. Spatial averaging and statistical comparisons were conducted to determine the variation in pollutant concentrations between pre-COVID and COVID-19 lockdown periods.

The 3-year baseline (2017-2019) provides a practical reference for comparison, though formal statistical significance testing is limited by the small sample size. To assess whether 2020 values represent meaningful departures from normal variability, we examined whether lockdown period concentrations fell outside the range of individual yearly values from 2017-2019.

All the datasets were averaged across Nigeria's entire land area (between longitudes 3°–15°E and latitudes 4°–14°N) using the regional selection tool on the Giovanni platform. This method allowed us to assess air quality changes on a national scale. The analysis focused on overall country-wide trends rather than individual cities or urban areas.

3. Results and Discussion

In March 2020 during the partial lockdown, the percentage variation of PM_{2.5} shows -76.16% drastic decrease compared with the mean value of the month of March for the three previous years, NO₂ shows a decrease of -6.57% in the same month. There was a 2.40% and 0.899% increase in SO₂ and O₃ concentration respectively as shown in table 1.

Even with the sharp 72.16% drop in March 2020, the PM_{2.5} level 77.758 µg/m³ was still far above the WHO's safe limit of 15 µg/m³ for 24-hour exposure. This means that although the lockdown led to a noticeable air quality improvement, pollution levels in Nigeria were still unhealthy by global standards. It highlights just how the country's air pollution problem is, even when human activity is drastically reduced.

In April, during the total lockdown, compared to the average concentration values for the 2017, 2018 and 2019 monthly mean, there was a decrease of -16.374%, -1.095% and -4.682% for PM_{2.5}, SO₂ and NO₂ concentration respectively. So also, an increase of 0.473% was observed in O₃ concentration as shown in table 2.

In Nigeria, the rainy season's duration varies from south to north. The south experiences a longer rainy season, from March to November, whereas the north has a shorter season, typically from mid-May or June to September [28, 29]. The Particulate matter and some other pollutants are at their minimal level when the rainfall is at its peak, as observed in high percentage variation of PM_{2.5} in March compared to April even with total lockdown. The pandemic incidence started when the rainy season was about to commence in the country.

Table 1: Mean concentration and relative change of: PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO₂ and O₃ in Nigeria. Three-year monthly mean (2017–2019) and mean of March during partial lockdown

Air Pollutant	Three-year monthly mean (March 2017, 2018 & 2019)	Partial Lockdown (March 2020)	Relative Change (%)
PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	326.162	77.758	-76.160
SO ₂ (µg/m ³)	0.379	0.388	+ 2.400
NO ₂ (1cm ²)x 10 ¹²	894.763	835.959	- 6.572
O ₃ (DU)	261.689	264.042	+ 0.899

NO₂ units (1/cm²) × 10¹² represent tropospheric column density in molecules per square centimeter. DU = Dobson Units, a measure of total column ozone.

To better understand these changes, the average PM_{2.5} levels in March during the baseline years (2017–2019) ranged between [309–389] µg/m³. In contrast, March 2020 recorded a much lower concentration of 77.758 µg/m³, a drop far beyond what would normally occur from year to year.

Likewise, the April 2020 PM_{2.5} level of 62.319 µg/m³ was notably lower than the baseline range for April [71–85] µg/m³. These sharp decreases point clearly to the impact of the COVID-19 lockdown on reducing emissions, rather than being a result of normal annual variation.

Table 2: Mean concentration and relative change of: PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO₂ and O₃ in Nigeria. Three-year monthly mean (2017–2019) and mean of April during total lockdown

Air Pollutant	Three-year monthly mean (April 2017, 2018 & 2019)	Total Lockdown (April 2020)	Relative Change (%)
PM _{2.5} ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	74.521	62.319	- 16.374
SO ₂ ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	0.366	0.362	- 1.095
NO ₂ ($1\text{cm}^{-2} \times 10^{12}$)	964.332	919.184	- 4.682
O ₃ (DU)	265.607	266.864	+ 0.473

NO₂ units ($1/\text{cm}^2$) $\times 10^{12}$ represent tropospheric column density in molecules per square centimeter. DU = Dobson Units, a measure of total column ozone.

Figure 2 (a – d) shows bar charts comparing the average monthly levels of each pollutant during the 2017–2019 baseline period with those recorded in 2020, making it easy to see how much the concentrations of PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO₂, and O₃ changed during the lockdown.

Figure 3 illustrates the percentage change between the partial lockdown period (March 2020) and the pre-lockdown average (2017–2019). Among all pollutants, PM_{2.5} showed the most significant drop, highlighting the clear impact of reduced human activity.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 2: Bar charts of comparisons between monthly means for 3-year observations before lockdown (2017 – 2019) and lock down period, 2020 for pollutants: (a)PM_{2.5} (b)SO₂ (c)NO₂ (d)Ozone

Fig. 3: Relative change plot comparing the percentage differential of the partial lockdown mean observations from pre-lockdown mean observations

Since the drops in PM_{2.5} and NO₂ levels during the lockdown were much greater than the normal year-to-year changes seen between 2017 and 2019, it's clear that these improvements were largely due to reduced human activities, not just random weather changes.

The comparison reveals pollutant-specific responses to the COVID-19 lockdown in Nigeria as shown in figures 2 and 3. The most pronounced change occurred in PM_{2.5} levels, which declined by approximately -75% in March 2020 relative to the pre-lockdown average for March 2017–2019. This sharp decrease reflects the immediate effect of lockdown measures on primary emission sources such as vehicular traffic, industrial operations, and open burning. In April 2020, the decline was less severe (~-15%), suggesting seasonal influences. Similar trends have been reported globally, where PM_{2.5} showed substantial reductions due to mobility restrictions [30].

SO₂ levels remained largely unchanged in March 2020 compared to the baseline, implying that sulfur-based emission sources, such as thermal power plants and certain industrial facilities, continued to operate during the early lockdown phase. However, a modest reduction (~-5%) was observed in April 2020, likely associated with reduced industrial throughput as restrictions persisted.

NO₂ concentrations fell by about -8% in March 2020 relative to the baseline, consistent with reduced vehicular activity during lockdown. By April 2020, the reduction was minimal, indicating possible increases in essential transportation and industrial processes. Since NO₂ is strongly associated with combustion-related activities, the limited reductions suggest that certain emission sources remained active.

Ozone displayed a different pattern. There was an increase in March and April 2020 concentrations compared to the baseline. Generally, NO₂ reduction increases ozone concentrations in the total column, due to reduced NO

titration. This aligns with the “ozone paradox” reported during COVID-19 lockdowns worldwide; ozone levels increased slightly as NO₂ concentrations decreased [31, 32, 33].

The observed pollutant-specific trends highlight the complexity of atmospheric responses to emission changes. While lockdown measures resulted in notable PM_{2.5} reductions, SO₂ and NO₂ changes were smaller due to ongoing activity in key sectors. The combined decrease in PM_{2.5}, SO₂, and NO₂ leads to substantial improvements in air quality, reducing human health risks and environmental damage. Meanwhile, an increase in total column ozone improves atmospheric protection against UV radiation, but rising ground-level ozone can offset some of these benefits. Therefore, air quality management requires integrated approaches that consider multiple pollutants and their chemical interactions.

It is important to emphasize that the COVID-19 lockdown represents a unique 'natural experiment' rather than a controlled study. The observed air quality improvements resulted from a complex interplay of factors including reduced anthropogenic emissions, seasonal meteorological patterns (particularly the transition from dry to rainy season in Nigeria), and the continued operation of essential services. While the lockdown's impact on emission sources is substantial and evident, the relative contributions of policy-driven emission reductions versus natural seasonal variations cannot be precisely quantified with the available data. This complexity underscores the value of integrated monitoring approaches combining satellite observations, ground-based measurements, and meteorological modeling.

3.1 Study Limitations

This study has a few limitations that should be recognized.

First, the analysis is based on satellite and reanalysis data that have relatively coarse spatial resolutions (0.5° × 0.625° for MERRA-2 and 0.25° for OMI). These datasets are useful for observing national trends but may not capture the finer, city-level variations in air quality. For instance, the lockdown effects in major cities like Lagos, Abuja, Kano, and Port Harcourt were probably stronger than the national average reflected in this study. However, because of the data limitations, a broader national approach had to be used.

Second, the study used a three-year baseline period (2017–2019), mainly due to data availability. With only three years of monthly data to compare against, it is difficult to clearly separate the lockdown's impact from natural year-to-year fluctuations. Weather conditions—such as harmattan dust intensity, rainfall onset, and changes in atmospheric circulation—varied between 2020 and

previous years, and these differences could have influenced air quality independently of human activity.

Third, the PM_{2.5} data from MERRA-2 primarily represents dust surface mass concentration, meaning it mostly measures mineral dust. While this is important for understanding Nigeria's air quality, especially during the dry season when Saharan dust transport is high, it doesn't fully capture human-related pollution from vehicles, industries, and biomass burning. Therefore, the connection between dust-based PM_{2.5} and total PM_{2.5} should be interpreted with caution.

Finally, Nigeria currently lacks a consistent network of ground-based air quality monitoring stations. This limitation makes it difficult to validate the satellite-based findings with direct, on-site measurements. It is also worth noting that some essential services, such as power generation, hospitals, security agencies, and limited commercial activities, continued to operate during the lockdown. These ongoing emissions likely contributed to the smaller observed changes in SO₂ and NO₂ compared to the more pronounced reductions in PM_{2.5}.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

The COVID-19 pandemic, which led to a nationwide lockdown in Nigeria starting on March 30, 2020, created a unique opportunity to observe how changes in human activity affect air quality.

The ensuing COVID-19 lockdown not only served as a public health measure but also yielded noticeable environmental benefits due to reduced human activity. Although many of these environmental improvements may be temporary, they underscore the opportunity for governments and individuals to adopt long-term pollution control practices. Interestingly, ozone (O₃) concentrations increased during the lockdown, a phenomenon attributed to decreased nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) emissions that limit ozone consumption, leading to elevated ambient ozone levels.

Since PM_{2.5} showed the greatest reductions during lockdown, long-term strategies should prioritize mitigating its dominant sources, such as vehicular emissions, open waste burning, and industrial activities. The persistence of SO₂ and NO₂ during lockdown suggests that power generation and essential industrial operations are major contributors. Cleaner energy adoption, fuel quality improvement, and emission-control technologies should be emphasized in these sectors. Public awareness of air quality in Nigeria and the world at large can significantly contribute to reducing emission levels, especially to transport companies and other air polluted companies in the country.

The differences observed between the pandemic and non-pandemic periods could be even more pronounced when analyzed with ground-based station data. Similar findings have been reported in Salé City, Morocco [15], São Paulo State, Brazil [33], and across East Asia, including Wuhan, Seoul, and Tokyo [34], among others. To capture real-time dynamics, investment in both ground-based and satellite air quality monitoring systems is essential, particularly in urban centers with high population exposure.

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Analyses and visualizations used in this paper were produced with the Giovanni online data system (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/giovanni/>), a web-based platform developed and maintained by the NASA Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center (GES DISC).

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